

A 3-D CAD Tool for CT Colonography

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Abstract—Nowadays, biomedical images of the human body are an invaluable source of information that clinicians can use in order to make a correct and final diagnosis. Their use is widespread in almost every branch of medicine. In some cases, computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) tools have received approval for being used without any human intervention and validation, like, for example, in breast cancer detection relying on X-rays mammograms. In this paper we present a framework for building CAD tools based on the well-known software design patterns and an implementation of the first modules of a CAD tool for computed tomography (CT) colonography.

I. INTRODUCTION

Within the current clinical settings, many diagnostic protocols rely on biomedical images. Almost every examination requires the acquisition of one or more images of the human body in a single or multiple modalities. As technology advances and imaging hardware gets cheaper, the number of images acquired in a single examination increases. Since almost every imaging modality is able to acquire fine details of the imaged body part, a correct diagnosis requires a careful reading of the entire image dataset. The workload for radiologists is increasing: they must inspect several high-resolution images, many times trying to merge the information extracted from the different modalities. Furthermore, the widespread use of three-dimensional (3-D) imaging modalities require the radiologists to inspect hundreds of images for every single examination.

It is clear that reliable and specialized software programs, known as computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) tools, might be a valuable aid in the diagnostic procedure:

- they might be used to get a second reading of the data. The clinicians can thus verify their conclusions and revise them if needed.
- They are necessary to build 3-D views of tomographic examinations, like computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and to merge the views built from data acquired in different modalities.
- They can provide useful hints that can potentially reduce the number of human errors caused by fatigue and/or habituation.

For the reasons outlined above, several research groups propose innovative schemes and tools that could be used in the clinical practice. The interest in this field, that should

be, in our opinion, considered as relevant per se, kept rising after a CAD tool has been approved for clinical use by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration.

In this paper we present a software tool for 3-D reconstruction of the colon based on the known and common software design patterns. Our goal is to provide a flexible and extensible tool that can be easily adapted to various image-based analysis. Our proposal, in fact, allows to easily modify every single feature and behaviour: from the data processing and viewing to the input-output routines of the human-computer interaction. The documentation on the modules subsystem contains unified modeling language (UML) diagrams.

The paper is organized as follows. In section II, we describe the components of generic CAD tools and briefly summarize the requirements that such tools should satisfy. In section III, we describe the approach we chose to engineer our tool. In section IV, we describe the implemented image-processing algorithms for the processing of CT colonographies and describe the graphical user interface of the tool.

II. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

Any CAD tool should be implemented in order to satisfy the following general requirements:

- the data, as stored by the acquisition device, should be read and reorganized as to reflect the way radiologists think about patients. The input subsystem, in fact, should be easily updated in order to gather information from different sources without making the users aware of the physical and logical organization of the data.
- The data must be visualized in the modality preferred by the radiologists. In case of tomographic data, it is important to offer a 3-D views of the data.
- The radiologists should be able to integrate all the information available. They should easily be able to move across visualizations and integrate other information.
- If the tool is supposed to aid the diagnosis, it should allow to extract region of interest (ROI) both in two and in three dimensions.
- If the tool is supposed to use machine learning approaches for the classification of the selected ROIs, the tool should offer functionalities needed to prepare the datasets used for training the classifiers.

Due to the complexity of a CAD tool, if easy updating and extensions are the major objectives, its project must be careful engineered. Obviously, in some cases, a software engineer needs to come to various compromises, for example between performance and flexibility, in order to reach his goal. Our system is composed by three major subsystems:

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data input, data presentation and visualization, and user interaction.

The data input subsystem is responsible to read the files stored and organized by the acquisition devices according to the DICOM standard [1]. The DICOM standard allows for a great variability in the logical and physical organization of the data: datasets stored by different hardware can present great differences. We have modeled the DICOM entities and provided a uniform organization of the data to the client modules of the data input subsystem. Since DICOM entities have been proposed with the aim of modeling the hospital workflow, this subsystem can easily be adapted to different encoding schemes, like, for example, the ANALYZE format, without modifying its external interface.

The data presentation and visualization subsystem is responsible to show on the user monitor the images read by the input subsystem. We subdivided this subsystem into two modules. The first module provides general functionalities for an interactive application (mouse and keyboard input, dispatching of the events among the different views,...). The second module is specialized for displaying the image data: it allows the visualization of single slices of a tomographic dataset, in different projections, along with the 3-D reconstruction of the dataset.

The user interaction subsystem is responsible to dispatch the user commands to the correct software components. In fact, a specific user action can be mapped onto different actions depending on, for example, the current view showed by the system. The explicit management of the user-generated events allows for an easier extension of the system when more task-dependent algorithm implementations are needed.

Each subsystem has been designed according a compositional scheme using the ‘design patterns’ approach. Such choice allows us to reduce the number of subclasses that needs to be implemented and obtain an easier software reuse with respect to standard approaches, like subclassing, multiple heredity, or other language-specific functionalities.

III. DESIGN PATTERNS

Design patterns attempt to solve the problem of code reusability with object-oriented programming. When a good solution for a specific problem is found by a software engineer, the same code is repeatedly used for similar problems with only task-specific modifications. Design patterns are a way to transfer the experience about “good ways” to organize the code into a logical and complete framework. A pattern describes a problem which occur very often in the domain of interest and describes a solution to that problem. A design pattern has four essential elements [2]:

- a name, used as a handle to describe a design problem, its solution and its consequences.
- The problem, that describes when the design pattern should be used. In some cases, we can find a list of conditions that should be met before applying the pattern.
- The solution, that describes the elements of the design. It describes the responsibilities and the interactions

among the various elements composing it.

- The consequences, describing the results and the trade-offs of applying this particular pattern.

In some cases, the solution specified by many design patterns could be implemented using the primitive mechanisms provided by the programming language itself. The use of a specific design pattern:

- makes it easier to understand the problem even for programmers who do not know the language used for the actual implementation;
- by explicitly introducing components to mimic implicit functionalities of the programming language, thus improving code readability, makes easier the maintenance and the extension of the code.

An example of used design patterns is the “Mediator”. A complex application is made of many independent components communicating each other. If the components are implemented in such a way that they know each other, it is very difficult to modify the communication protocol without reading the code of each one of them. The Mediator pattern requires the design and the implementation of an object whose sole responsibility is to route the messages that the various modules send each other. The Mediator module can be considered an abstraction of the cooperation strategy that does not require the knowledge about the internal mechanisms producing the messages that it dispatches. If the cooperation needs to be modified or new modules are added to system, only the Mediator module must be modified.

IV. A TOOL FOR THE VIRTUAL COLONOGRAPHY

The greater part of malignant tumors developing in the colon stems from adenomatous polyps. The patient will not develop a malignant tumor, if a polyp is early detected (when the dimensions are not clinically significant) and removed. It is clear the importance of a screening program on people presenting an average and high risk for colon cancer. Today such screening could be potentially performed with CT colonography (the results of large clinical trials, as the American ACRIN and the Italian IMPACT, will be published soon). Since the datasets produced by CT colonographies are very large, a valid tool supporting the analysis of such large datasets could speed up the inspection process and allow a greater number of patients to undergo periodic screening examinations.

We built, upon the modeling presented in the previous section, the initial modules of a CAD system for the detection of polyps in a CT examination of the colon. The current implementation, besides obvious input functionalities, offers:

- 2-D filtering of the CT slices.
- 3-D reconstruction of the complete colon.
- Navigation through the colon and 3-D region of interest (ROI) extraction.

A. 2-D Filtering

The 3-D reconstruction is based on a surface rendering approach, called Marching Cubes [3]. Such algorithm constructs isosurfaces, i.e. surfaces composed by voxels with a

Fig. 1. Results of the 2-D foreground/background segmentation. From the upper left corner, clockwise: original image; thresholded and binarized image; edge detection using image erosion and subtraction; largest region detected; result of the hole filling procedure applied on the largest region; binary mask corresponding to the foreground object; final segmentation.

Fig. 2. Noise in the 2-D slices. From the upper left corner, clockwise: partial volume effect (PVE), path A crosses a region without any PVE, while path B crosses a region with a strong PVE; noise in the areas corresponding to the colon (the signal coming from internal colon volume should be black); graphs of the intensity values along the paths A and B in the first image.

constant intensity value (or isovalue). Before the Marching Cube may construct the isosurfaces, the images need to be filtered by two steps:

- the foreground image must be separated from the background.
- The areas, in the 2-D slices, that might correspond to the colon, must be filtered in order to remove partial volume effects (PVE) and to be characterized by a homogeneous intensity value.

The foreground/background image separation is performed by using operators of the Mathematical Morphology [4]. The 2-D slice is first thresholded by using a threshold value computed by the image histogram and then binarized. The external border of the image is computed by eroding the binary image. The edges are then linked and the largest region, corresponding to the entire area containing the body, is selected for hole filling. Fig. 1 shows an example of the application of the previous steps.

Fig. 3. Example of the results obtained by the anisotropic diffusion filtering. Left picture: segmented 2-D slice without any filtering. The inner, darker regions show a strong presence of noise, the large white area is caused by the intensity window parameters. Right picture: image obtained by the application of the described anisotropic filter. The inner regions show a (more) homogeneous gray level. Such homogeneity is needed by the Marching Cube algorithm for a correct selection of isovalues in the computation of the isosurfaces.

Since the marching cube algorithm relies on the comparison of the intensity values in order to discriminate among isosurfaces, we need to remove the noise present in the image in order to get reliable results. Fig. 2 shows two different problems that can force a failure in the Marching Cubes process:

- the signal coming from the volume inside the colon (internal circular-shaped dark areas) should have the same intensity as the air.
- Since pixels of the 2-D slices correspond to volume elements, they can suffer from partial volume effects in areas very close to the colon surface.

Our idea is to make those intensity values more homogeneous and then apply the Marching Cube. We applied an anisotropic filter [5] on the entire (segmented) image. The filter propagates the intensity values inside regions and avoids blurring strong edges. After few applications, the regions are more homogeneous while the overall structure of the image (edges) is preserved. An example of the application of the filter is shown in Fig. 3

B. 3-D Reconstruction

There are two main approaches to 3-D volume reconstruction: surface rendering and volume rendering. We chose a surface rendering approach for the following reasons:

- it requires less computational resources than volume rendering. Furthermore, surface rendering allows us to exploit the hardware acceleration offered by many graphics cards.
- It offers an abstraction of the morphology of the objects. 3-D structures corresponding to polyps will be mainly classified according to their morphology [6]. Intensity-based analysis of suspicious areas can be performed on original data using the set of 2-D slices.

Marching Cubes uses cubic voxels: each vertex of the cube is associated to the intensity value of the corresponding 2-D slice. Given a particular isovalue, the algorithm check if the cube is crossed by the corresponding isosurface and, if it is, it splits the cubes and represents the various regions as triangles. All the extracted isosurfaces are finally connected.

Fig. 4. From the upper left corner, clockwise: 3-D structure that includes the colon and the lungs; structure corresponding to lungs; 3-D view of the colon structure without lungs; same structure of the previous image from a different viewpoint; volume with small 3-D structures caused by noise; same volume of the previous image after the removal of the smaller regions.

Fig. 5. The picture shows the current graphical user interface of the application. The main window is subdivided into three panels. In the left column: 2-D slice and 3-D reconstruction of the colon; in the right column: the inner structures of the colon, as they were computed in the 3-D construction process. The current position under inspection is shown in each view (red marks): the 3-D colon structure is rendered as semi-transparent in order to allow the radiologist to see the red mark if it falls in an inner region. The radiologist can select a 3-D ROI in the right column (blue parallelepiped), which is highlighted also in the global 3-D colon structure. After the selection of the ROI, the radiologist can ask the tool to store it in a dataset that will be used to train a classifier.

The simple application of the Marching Cubes algorithm produces a volume containing irrelevant structures, such as the one corresponding to the lungs and other noisy ones. In fact, small noisy areas can force the algorithm to construct small regions that should not be included in the segmented volume corresponding to the colon.

Our tool removes both the structures corresponding to the lungs and the small structures caused by noise. Fig. 4 shows the results of the execution of the algorithm on a dataset¹.

C. Navigation and 3-D ROI extraction

Once the 3-D structure corresponding to the colon has been built, the tool displays a main window subdivided into

three panels (Fig. 5), showing the 2-D slices, the global 3-D structure, and the colon from the corresponding internal part of the built 3-D volume. The radiologist can explore the entire volume by interacting with any of the three views. In fact, the typical analysis performed in reading a CT colonography requires the radiologist to explore the inner structures of the colon searching for suspicious polyp-like structures both in 2-D and in 3-D.

If the radiologist detects a suspicious volume, either in 2-D or in 3-D, it can select a ROI, in 2-D or in 3-D. The selected ROI will be used to prepare a dataset of human-labeled suspicious 3-D structures (and their corresponding values in the 2-D original dataset). In the future, once a good dataset has been built, various classifiers can be trained, evaluated, and implemented in the tool in order to offer a valid support to the diagnosis.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Computer-aided diagnosis tools are a valuable support to the current radiological practice due to the increasing resolution and dimension of the data that a radiologist needs to inspect before providing a diagnosis. Their software architecture is very complex and hard to maintain and extend. Quite often, the logical organization and the interactions of the software modules composing the CAD tool are based on the characteristics of the programming language used in the first implementation. If code readability, extensibility, and reusability are considered important features, this is not necessarily the best choice. Software design patterns, which can be considered a formalization of good and tested software development practices, represent a valid framework.

In this paper we described an implementation of the first modules of a CAD tool for the analysis of CT colonographies based on design patterns. This project will allow us to continue our work along two main directions: software development using the described design patterns and the implemented modules can generate different CAD tools; image analysis of CT colonographies that we are now collecting in order to create a large datasets of polyp and non-polyp 3-D structures. Such dataset will be used to train classifiers to discriminate among the various types of lesions that the colon can suffer from.

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¹We used the VCG library by the Visual Computing Lab, ISTI, CNR, Pisa. The library is available at <http://vcg.isti.cnr.it>.